

The Female Bildungsroman: The Study of Krupabai Saththianadhan

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ABSTRACT

This article proposes that the autobiographical novels Krupabai Saththianadhan wrote can be considered bildungsroman novels, in which the protagonists evolve into mature personalities by the end of the novel. A bildungsroman is a story of the growing up of a sensitive person, who finds answers to his/her questions through maturity. Generally, such a novel begins with a loss or tragedy that emotionally disturbs the main character. The protagonist gains maturity through a series of life experiences. Saguna's account of her relationship with her mother and her experiences of the loss of her child is the basis of this analysis.

Keywords: Bildungsroman, Autobiographical, Alienation, Survival

FULL RESEARCH PAPER**Introduction**

This article studies Krupabai Satthianadhan's autobiographical novels *Saguna: The Story of Native Christian Life* (1887-1888) and *Kamala: The Story of Hindu Life*, which was first published serially in the *Madras Christian College Magazine* in 1894. The life experiences Satthianadhan portrays in these novels are significantly autobiographical, so much so that *Saguna* is considered the first autobiographical novel in India, written by an Indian woman writer. *Saguna's* account of her relationship with her mother and her experiences of the loss of her child is the basis of my analysis. As female bildungsromans, these coming-of-age stories tell us about how women struggled with patriarchal norms.

Literature Review

Nineteenth-century autobiographies often depict the suppression of female autonomy by patriarchal norms and show women who, during their lifetime, struggled with the labels of being a good mother, a good wife and a good daughter. The women's question emerged during the national movement as a political question to be addressed to give shape to the vision of a free Indian nation. Vina Mazumdar writes, "In the first phase, the women's question emerged essentially in the context of the identity crisis of the new educated middle class--the first product of the colonial system of education. Many of them, trying to imitate the lifestyles of the colonial rulers, found the condition of their own women to be a stumbling block" (Mazumdar 1). She divides the history of the women's question in India into many phases. In the second phase, the women's question got coloured by the rise of cultural nationalism and revivalism as an attack to the spread of western influences and values in our society: "The cultural nationalists...introduced a new concept into the women's question--women as the custodians of traditional cultural values (Mazumdar 2) examine the influence of these nationalist propositions on the practices of mothering in this chapter. "To begin with the definition" Bildungsroman" is of German Origin" (Golban 10)" the hero or heroine who has to reach fulfilment and harmony by passing through various conflicts of life, and succeeding and interrelated stages of growth and maturation" (Golban 10) " Martin Swales says that it not necessary for a novel to have an happy ending for it to be called Bildungsroman" (Golban 10)

Michael Bakhtin argues that novels considered Erziehungsroman or Bildungsromane (novels of education) vary widely in their themes and focus; some are biographical or autobiographical, while others are not. In certain novels, the emphasis

is on the educational aspect of the protagonist's development, while in others the story focuses more on the hero's chronological progression.

Bakhtin discusses the Bildungsroman as a novelistic genre focused on human emergence or development. He emphasises that this type of novel, often created around personal growth, can also be described through terms like "becoming", "formation" and the German concept of "Bildung". Essentially, Bakhtin views the Bildungsroman as a narrative that explores self-discovery and maturation. (Golban 14) Bildungsroman (Novel of formation). A coming-of-age story that centres on the protagonist's emotional, intellectual, and moral growth, often involving a significant transformation. (Golban 17)

Discussion

Saguna can be considered a Bildungsroman novel as the character is highly individualised, independent and able to fulfil her goals. *Saguna* is a novel that traces the protagonist's development as she navigates her childhood, marriage, motherhood and diverse experiences of growth into a mature person. In its broader sense, the bildungsroman is a genre that focuses on the protagonist's psychological and moral growth from youth to adulthood. *Saguna: The story of Native Christian Life* is the first Indian New Woman autobiographical novel written in English (Sathianadhan, 1). "The term applies to the Indian woman who emerged during the later nineteenth century as a consequence of British colonialist influences, which included educational and socio-religious reforms. Defying institutionalised patriarchal ideologies that enforced her domesticity and subjectivity, the New-woman sought greater equality between men and women" (Sathianadhan 1). *Saguna* is the new woman in the novel. She is shown to be a very intelligent girl. She is closest to her elder brother Bhasker. Her life is marked by movement and change. *Saguna* is a semi- autobiographical novel. There are elements of her own life narrated in the novel. The protagonist remembers the past and narrates it through memory. *Saguna*, being an educated girl, pities girls whose sole aim in life is to get married. The protagonist *Saguna* receives guidance from many mentors, making it a classical Bildungsroman.

"Generally, people get confused with life narrative and fiction. People call autobiographical texts "novels", although they rarely call novels "autobiographies. When a writer narrates about his/her life, it is not a novel; calling 'life narrative' 'nonfiction confuses rather than solves the matter. Life narratives and novels have the same characteristics. There is a plot, dialogue, setting, characters, protagonists, and many writers blur the boundary line between autobiography and the novel. (Smith

13,14) Bildungsroman has been taken up more recently by women and other disenfranchised persons to consolidate a sense of emerging identity and to gain greater place in public life. The Bildungsroman can also be used negatively as a norm of assimilation into the dominant culture that is unattainable and must be relinquished, or that produces alienation from the home community. In many women's writing, the plot of development culminates not in integration but in an awakening to gender based limitations. (Smith 190)

From the late eighteenth century, the Bildungsroman is the form taken by the European novel. Its key narrative is the storytelling part. In this Bildungsroman, a young man/woman from the provinces comes to the city to make it good and gains education and becomes worldly wise and gradually becomes reconciled to it, but modifications are there for the young woman; she undergoes worldly or sentimental education, and she becomes reconciled and settled, maybe in marriage. A young man or woman undergoes a process of aesthetic, worldly or sentimental education; it is possible to undergo all three together and achieve fame as a writer or artist. There is also a modified version in which the novel ends tragically: the protagonist either fails or dies. Further, in the expansion of the genre, the Bildungsroman is present in movies and visual media. It is not a limited genre but has continued power, unlike Bakhtin, who defines it as mapping the story of the young boy and girl onto a historically changing world and then coming to terms with it. It is a mapping in which both the reader and the author gain wisdom from the text.

Applying the above Bildungsroman theory to Saguna, it can be called a female Bildungsroman story: Saguna, with the help of a Western education, gains knowledge, goes out into the world, travels alone by train without an escort, and receives education at Saththianadhan's home. The journey doesn't end on a happy note: she has to leave her medical education halfway. She goes to rest at her sister's place, and her journey is mapped against the changing historical times as Saguna gains maturity. She meets Samuel Saththianadhan, falls in love with him, marries him and eventually it ends tragically, as she dies in the novel and in real life. Autogynography. Domna C. Stanton's essay is the subject of difference. Proposed this term to suggest the centrality of gendered subjectivity to the literary production of self-referential acts. Although Stanton offered a postmodern critique of the unexamined belief in referentiality, she argues that the textuality of the psychic splitting of women's subjectivity must be located in her "different status in the symbolic order." And she concludes that women's "gendered narrative involved a different plotting and configuration of the split subject." Stanton notes that, at the moment of second-wave

feminism in which she was writing, "gender of the author" "did make a difference" because the refusal of the referential status of the signature threatened to perpetuate "female anonymity"(Smith 187)

In the Autoethnographic mode of life narrative, according to Mary Louise Pratt, "colonised subjects undertake to represent themselves in ways that engage with the colonizer's own terms. Pratt argues that indigenous or oppressed subjects, in taking up writing, may both collaborate with and appropriate a colonizer's (or dominant culture's) discursive models, thereby "transculturating" them into indigenous idioms and producing hybrid forms of collectivised life narrative. Autoethnography emphasises "how subjects are constituted in and by their relations to each other" in "the contact zone" of cultural encounter, and how the identities of dominant and subordinated subjects interlock and interact despite histories of radically uneven power relations. "Autobiography" from "autobiographical fiction" may be an interplay between the two modes.

Kamala: A Story of Hindu Life was first published in serial form in the *Madras Christian College Magazine* in 1894. It was published posthumously as a book in the same year by Srinivasa, Varadachari and Co., Madras. The novel was well-received when both Indian and British readers first published it. It was translated into the Tamil language in 1896. Kamala is also the story of the author's own life. The motherhood experience of both Kamala and Krupabai Sattianadhan is the same. The author, when writing the Novel *Kamala*, was on her deathbed and feared that she would not be able to complete it. Both the semi-autobiographical novels can be read as conversion novels. It focuses on the experience that conversion had on motherhood. Motherhood transforms the lives of all the characters. By examining the novels, one can glimpse Hindu and Christian motherhood. In *Kamala*, the author has lost her infant baby; she immortalises her daughter in the narrative of *Kamala*. The author, as a Christian mother and *Kamala*, as a Hindu mother, face the same agony.

Kamala fictionalises the tough and contemporary issues of child marriage and early motherhood. It is also a psychological novel that explores the mindsets of both *Kamala* and the author, Sattianadhan. The author tries to release *Kamala* from the mould of child-wife and widow, and to introduce her to Western feminist individualism.

As a societal novel, *Kamala* depicts the life of a high-caste Hindu woman in nineteenth-century India, aiming to awaken the reader's moral principles. There are many occurrences in the novel that need social reform regarding women's condition

as a child-bride in her in-laws' home. It throws light on certain socio-religious customs and manners. One of her reasons for doing this was to accustom foreign readers to indigenous patriarchal institutions and structures and their expectations of Indian women. The novel was written for the British readership and English-educated indigenous readers. The relationship between a husband and wife in an orthodox Hindu home is described in detail. They do not have the liberty to talk to each other. The duties of the Hindu wife and the joint family system are the novel's themes. A child-bride's and a Hindu wife's duties are described in detail. She has to cover her face while doing her duties. Her mother-in-law and sister-in-law constantly harass her. She is miserable in her husband's home. Sathianadhan uses the phrase " crude Hinduism time and again in the novel, showing her direct engagement with Christian and colonialist politics.

The "New Woman" in Krupabai Sathianadhan's *Kamala: A Story of Hindu Life*

Kamala, the protagonist, is portrayed as belonging to the old order. In her character, we find the seeds and thirst for knowledge and reading. She is a lover of nature, and in the novel, page after page is devoted to its description; we find that Kamala is very happy and one with nature. She forgets all her grief when she is outside her home.

Motherhood: Motherhood brings happiness and fulfilment to Kamala, but when she sees that Ganesh is very indifferent to the child, she feels deeply hurt, and the final strain in their relationship comes when Ganesh says the child is not his, but he is sure the father of the child is Ramchander. This hurts Kamala's ego, and after confronting her husband, she just leaves his house in the middle of the night with her daughter. In this section, I focus on how the experience of conversion shapes the portrayal of motherhood, how these novels relate to the new woman question, and the female bildungsroman aspect of the novels. Concepts of motherhood and mothering are depicted in Kamala. In Kamala, we see the mothering of Kamala's mother-in-law. She has mothered her son Ganesh very strictly. He listens to her and is very obedient to her. Ganesh is well educated; he has studied in an English medium school and is exposed to city life. He has a government job. Hence, Kamala's mother-in-law's mothering is a fulfilling experience. She is very strict with her daughter-in-law. Kamala gives birth to a daughter, named Droupadi, on the seventh day after her birth. As her baby is a girl, her sister-in-law starts harassing her, saying that whoever wanted a child just now, that too is a girl. When Kamala listens to these abuses, she holds her baby to her bosom tightly; she is afraid that these curses may fall on her baby. When her husband, Ganesh, comes to visit her, he ignores the baby, which hurts Kamala

deeply. Kamala sings a lullaby for her daughter, 'Sleep, my child, sleep!' which sounded like a death song rather than a lullaby. She sings this lullaby to her dying child:" Golden is thy cradle, wide thy father's sway. Gently slumber, sweet one, sweet one, Harm is far away. Sleep, little one, sleep. Bending o'er thy cradle, All to thee unknown, Kindly spirits hover, Seen by Heaven alone. Sleep, little one, sleep". Here, the authorial voice interrupts 'And did she know that the infant spirit had taken to its wings when she was singing the tear-woven melody? Here, the autobiographical element is discernible as the author also faced the agony of losing her only child. For Kamala, her mothering is unfulfilled, and motherhood and childbirth are painful for her. Both Kamala and Saguna can be read as conversion novels. It traces Saguna's life narrative from childhood through her youth into her education. In a female bildungsroman, also called the bildungsroman of marginalised women, they write about their personal experiences. Saguna can be read as a conversion story in which Saguna meets Christian missionaries. She is a new woman, educated, well-travelled, and a Bible woman who teaches scripture to children.

Dialogues enrich the novel's narrative. The story is narrated in the third person. The author is omniscient. Kamala is a Bildungsroman novel. In the novel, Kamala matures from a shy, cheerful girl into a child bride and later into a good wife and mother. Her journey through life is delineated in great detail throughout the autobiographical novel. Her daughter dies, and later her husband dies too. But her decision to give away her inherited wealth to the needy makes it a Bildungsroman. The female character matures psychologically. Kamala is rich and is the heiress to a lot of property, which she has inherited from her mother. Kamala's mother was from a well-off family. She is described as possessing a lot of pearls, and as far as Kamala remembers, she always had her mother's pearls on her. Her friends also commented that it was strange to see Kamala wearing a pearl necklace. On her wedding day, the elderly woman also commented that Kamala's mother must have been rich to pass on the jewellery to her daughter. Kamala herself never knew about the riches or jewellery that her mother possessed, nor did she know that she was heiress to a lot of property. Kamala is also ignorant of the fact that, when she was born, her parents had promised to give her hand to Ramchander, who lived with them at the time and was the son of her uncle. Ramchander likes and loves Kamala. This he reveals to her when she becomes a widow. By that time, Kamala had made up her mind to leave all her property to welfare work and devote her life to society and charity.

Kamala is a perfect wife, daughter-in-law, and mother, according to the Hindu scriptures. Kamala is a 'pativrata' that is devoted and loyal to her husband. This is a

way of life that Hindu girls are brought up and reared right from childhood. This comes naturally to them. But the authorial voice seems quite critical when narrating the marriage ceremonies, specifically the ghatbandhan, in which Kamala was to be Ganesh's property henceforth, come what may. The idea that love may occur after marriage is ridiculed. Saguna. Thus, in Kamala and Saguna, an East-West encounter is clearly visible. The East is dark, mystical, full of the old order of things, whereas the West is portrayed as enlightened, educated, fast-moving. When one observes the social status of women around the globe in the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, the social evils that prevailed were similar. Women were not allowed to attend schools or universities. They were mostly trained at home by tutors. Women were trained to be homemakers.

Description of "nature" in *Kamala: A Story of a Hindu Life*

Kamala begins with these lines: "India may not be a perfect paradise, yet there are in it spots of surpassing beauty and grandeur. The mountainous part of the district of Nalgonda in the Deccan, where the Ganga and Godavari take their rise, is one such spot. Here nature is sublime in its majesty and rugged in its grandeur; here hills rise above hills, some verdure (greenery) clad, others bare, bleak and barren, with caves and caverns at their bases through which the waters leap in torrents in the rainy season. Here, not far from the chain of hills that form the glorious Western Ghats, is situated the sacred city to which I shall give the name Sivagunga" (Sattianadhan 22) ...in the glowing lights between the trees, the form of a little girl may be distinctly seen. It is that of Kamala, the daughter of the old Brahman recluse. She stands by the ruined temple that tops the hillock, her face resting on her hand, with a weary expression in her eyes. She seems to be gazing at the blue expanse of the plain below. At last, a sigh is heard, and the girl murmurs, 'Father is nowhere to be seen. Oh! When will he come home?' The great big idol stares at her from the temple, and the trees rustle mournfully overhead. Poor girl! her thoughts are hard to express... (Sattianadhan 22).

In the above opening lines of the novel, one can make out that the writer has given a lot of importance to the technique of writing. Nature is described very picturesquely. It is as if a canvas is painted for the reader. Mountains, rivers, caves, everything is described minutely. Kamala, the protagonist, is introduced to us on the first page of the first chapter. There are in all twenty chapters in the novel. Kamala, we are told, is the daughter of the old Brahman recluse. Her father is a sanyasi, one who has devoted his life to priestly affairs and is not a householder. After Kamala's mother's death, it is he who has been both her mother and father.

Hindu rites and rituals in Kamala

Krupabai Satthianadhan does not have a first-hand experience of a Hindu girl, as she is a Brahmin convert to Christianity. Her upbringing and teachings are in line with her religion and culture. Her identity, therefore, is of a Brahmin convert Christian author. One would not hope to find a clear delineation of Kamala as a Hindu girl in her novel. However, she writes from the beginning that her mother was a Hindu and that part of her remained a Hindu, and that she was full of the life of a Hindu girl, as her mother was born and brought up as a Hindu. The novel does not raise any controversial issues of conversion or deliberate conversion from one religion to another. The novel also does not judge any religion; rather, it focuses on the rich traditions and cultural diversity each religion offers. The fact that Krupabai wrote both the autobiographical novels one after the other proves that she very much wanted to write about her own country.

Conclusion

The times in which Krupabai Satthianadhan lived were not very favourable for women. The nineteenth century had strict Victorian rules and morals governing women's conduct in society. The girls were home-schooled. Women's education varied by religion and social class. Some women were able to access education, while others were expected to learn domestic skills. The British Government established girls' schools in Madras in 1871. By 1891, more than 48,000 girls began attending schools. Jyotibai Phule and his wife, Savitribai Phule, became pioneers of female education. Satthianadhan was far ahead of her time in terms of education. She portrayed the 'new woman' in her writings. The new woman who emerged during the early nineteenth century was aware of her rights, conscious of her position in the home, and eager to educate herself. The new woman had a thirst for knowledge and reading; she was totally involved in the issues of women of her time. She was a social activist. She contributed articles to newspapers, magazines and journals. "Krupabai holds the great distinction of introducing the Indian heroine into English fiction by Indian women" (Satthianadhan xii). With her autobiographical novel *Saguna: A Story of Native Christian Life*, she pioneers the Indian New Woman writing tradition in English" (Satthianadhan xii). Krupabai died in the year 1894. She was thirty-two years old. Krupabai is credited with writing the first semi-autobiographical novel in English. *Saguna: A Story of Native Christian Life*. Her second novel, *Kamala: A Story of Hindu Life*, is a sequel to her first semi- autobiographical novel, *Saguna: A Story of Native Christian Life*. Krupabai's bond with her elder brother, Bhasker, is reflected in the

delineation of both characters. Krupabai has borrowed the content of her chapters from her mother's life.

The experience of conversion had on the way motherhood is portrayed, how these novels are tied to the new woman question and the female bildungsroman aspect of the novel. In post-conversion autobiographical novels, the self observes and judges the earlier confused and unconverted self and accepts the present-day self as modern. The self does not engage in idol worship, fears the true God and believes in Monotheism. Conversion autobiographies were political acts of retrospection and self-construction. The conversion narrative offers converts a public space within which to redefine themselves in relation to caste, gender, religious and regional identities. This person was part of the project to modernise India. A high-caste Hindu who converts to another faith writes an autobiography of the self by remembering his/her past and provides guidelines for his/her fellow beings. The low-caste Hindu converts convert for economic reasons and may not be able to write their experiences for others to read and follow. The conversion narratives shed light on the rejection and rudeness they faced from family and society. But such may not be the case; some, over time, accept the converts into the family. Thus, this article examined Motherhood in its various cultural and religious contexts.

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